

IMPORTANT ASPECTS OF UZBEKISTAN'S INTERSTATE RELATIONS AND TRANSPORT IN EXPORT- IMPORT

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Abstract. This article describes in detail the importance of trade relations of the Republic of Uzbekistan with foreign countries, the role of trade and diplomatik relations with the world's leading developed countries in improving foreign economic relations, ie the role and advantages of transport in exports and imports.

Аннотация. В данной статье подробно описывается значение торговых отношений Республики Узбекистан с зарубежными странами, роль торгово-дипломатических отношений с ведущими развитыми странами мира в совершенствовании внешнеэкономических связей, т.е. роль и преимущества транспорта в экспорте и импорте.

Keywords: transport, railway, CIS. export, import,, foreign trade, science and technology revolution, economic relations.

Ключевые слова: транспорт, железная дорога, СНГ. экспорт, импорт, внешняя торговля, научно-техническая революция, экономические отношения.

Introduction. It is known that one of the main places in the development of any country is the transport sector. The Republic of Uzbekistan is one of the countries with well-developed transport opportunities. There are types of transport such as water (river), air, pipeline, land (car, railway). It plays an important role in the development of cultural relations between the countries. Transport and railway services are mainly effective for the development of interstate foreign trade.

The reason is that if the distance between the countries is close, it is better to use road transport, and if it is far, it is better to use railway transport.

By the end of 2020, the foreign trade turnover of the Republic of Uzbekistan amounted to 36,299.3 million US dollars, which is 5,451.7 million US dollars more than in 2019 (ie, 41,751.0 million dollars in 2019). or 13.1 percent, foreign trade turnover with the CIS countries decreased by 2 percent.

Export. By the end of 2020, the number of exporters of Uzbekistan was 6,109, and they exported products and products worth 9,323.3 million dollars. This indicator is 25.7% less than in 2019. In December 2020 alone, the export volume amounted to 930.4 million US dollars, which is 673.5 million dollars less than in December 2019.

Import. In 2020, the volume of imports amounted to 21,171.5 million US dollars, which is 87.2% more than in 2019. The most imported goods are transport equipment (37.6 percent), industrial goods - 16.9 percent, chemicals and similar products - 13.7 percent.

According to statistics, by 2019, Uzbekistan's foreign trade with the CIS countries will be much higher than in previous years.

One of the main reasons for this is the improvement of the transport system and the percentage of foreign trade with other countries. , Tajikistan 5.3%, Turkmenistan 2.3%, Ukraine 1.9% and the least exporting Belarus 0.8%, Azerbaijan 0.8% and Moldova 0.1%. Import percentages with other foreign countries and CIS countries are shown below. Russia 50.3%, Kazakhstan 23.6%, Turkmenistan 5.0%, Belarus 3.5%, Ukraine 3.2%, Tajikistan 1.9%, Kyrgyzstan 1.8%, Azerbaijan 0.3 % will import.

The bulk of these exports and imports were carried out through the following means of transport.

Pipeline transport. 650.6 million dollars.

Air transport b. \$527.1 million.

Railway transport. \$511.0 million.

Car transport. 23.2 million dollars. As a share of transport types.

Such convenient economic and social opportunities are available to everyone in Uzbekistan.

In the densely populated neighboring areas (Fergana Valley, Zarafshan, Lower Amudarya, Surkhandarya Region) many inter-republican regional production complexes of various specialties have been established. creates ample opportunities for the establishment of free economic zones.

Solving the cross-border river road problems in Central Asia will make the microgeographic location of the republic more convenient.

In the transport systems of developing countries, one or two types of transport are developed, while others are very backward. The footprint of railway networks in these countries is different, which increases the cost of freight and passenger transportation, hinders the development of interregional economic relations and generally slows down economic development. Below is the structure of export and import of foreign economic relations.

Table 1

Export composition.

	2016	2017	2018	2019
Cotton fiber	5.3	3.8	1.6	1.6
Food	5,7	7,0	7,8	8,8
Fruit and vegetables	4,6	5,1	6,3	6,9
Chemical products and articles used for them	7,0	7,0	6,5	5,0
Energy sources and oil products	14,2	12,8	19,1	14,5
Black metals	1,3	1,2	2,3	1,7
Non-ferrous metals	4,6	6,1	6,1	5,4
Machinery and	1,8	2,8	1,5	2,4

equipment				
Textiles and sewing products	7,6	9,0	9,3	9,3
Gold	23,2	26,0	20,8	28,2
Crevice	25,2	19,7	21,9	19,7
Others	3,5	4,6	3,1	3,3
Import composition.				
	2016	2017	2018	2019
Food	11,9	9,1	8,1	7,8
Chemical products and articles used for them.	17,5	15,3	13,0	13,2
Energy sources and oil products	4,9	5,3	4,5	3,9
Black metals	6,7	8,1	8,1	7,6
Non-ferrous metals	0,9	1,0	1,0	1,1
Machinery and equipment	41,3	36,1	43,0	43,8
Services	6,7	9,7	7,8	6,8
Others	10,2	11,0	11,2	12,7

Thus, in 40 years, the volume of world trade increased 10 times. The most important aspect of world trade was the changes in the composition of goods under the influence of geographical division of labor and scientific and technical progress. That is, the weight of fuel, raw materials, and food products is decreasing, and the weight of the products of fantalab production industries is increasing.

These changes took place in connection with the sharp decrease in the dependence of economically developed countries on the import of raw materials from developing countries. Uzbekistan has established strong cultural and economic relations with these developed countries.

For many countries of the world, international trade remains the main form of foreign economic relations. The degree of involvement in the international division of labor depends on the level of development of the productive forces. Due to this, industrialized countries occupy leading positions in international trade, specializing in the supply of high-tech products (machines, electronic equipment, pharmaceuticals and chemical products).

The development of science and technology plays a major role in the development of interstate relations. That is, it opens up new aspects of relations. The progress of science and technology has shown that nowadays transport is one of the most convenient and cheapest means of

communication. Nowadays, transport competes equally with its competitors and takes its place in the global economic relations.

In a short historical period, Uzbekistan has become an international trade and economic entity, gradually and successfully completing complex tasks such as entering into mutual relations, improving the structure of the national economy, developing industry, ensuring food, energy and transport security. is solving. country. Significant results were also achieved in the development of the transport system. The most important of them is that the integrity of the railway transport systems of the republic has been achieved. The territory of Uzbekistan stretches hundreds of kilometers from the north-west to the south-east, and the country's borders are separated by mountain ranges and wide ridges. Considering that it passes through deserts, we believe that this issue is an urgent strategic issue. komil. Large-scale works in the transport system are an integral part of efforts to further develop foreign economic relations of our country. Establishing foreign economic relations with 140 neighboring countries of the world is one of the most important trade partners of the Republic of Uzbekistan. These include the Russian Federation, China, Kazakhstan, the Republic of Korea, Turkey and European countries. The development of the transport system allows to expand the foreign economic activity of the republic in new geographical directions.

In order to increase the industrial production and export potential of the regions, to attract more foreign investments to our national economy, a number of new transport routes were built in the country in recent years at the initiative of the republican government.

In comparison with the neighboring countries - the Russian Federation, Afghanistan, Iran and the Caucasus, the meso-economic geographical position of Uzbekistan (relative to the neighboring regions) is distinguished by its average convenience. Every society pays great attention to effective territorial organization of its productive forces, first of all, industry, which is the leading branch of the national economy. Because industry, as a source of non-stop production of material and technical means for all sectors of the national economy, determines the economic potential of any region, the technical level of the entire social production, and the state of use of material and labor resources.

Various conditions and factors are involved in the development of industry and its territorial organization. They can be divided into two main groups: 1) economic-geographical factors 2) natural-geographical factors. Economic-geographical factors include the state of supply of labor resources and their characteristics, forms of social organization of production, energy, transport conditions, social forms of production, the material and technical base of production, level of FTT, and natural-geographical factors include natural conditions (relief , such as climate) features, the level of provision of natural resources (mineral and water resources). The importance of the transport sector in the industrial development of our country is also increasing.

The reason for such assessment of the economic geographical position of Uzbekistan in Meso is, on the one hand, with the republics of the Caucasus, in particular with the Russian Federation. largely effectively connected by modern means of transport and maintaining traditionally close multilateral ties with these countries. It is proof that Russia is the leader in the volume of export-import relations between the countries of the world. On the other hand, it is located in the south and in Uzbekistan, Afghanistan and Iran, which belong to the Mesoeconomic Geographical Group of countries, have been with our republic throughout the past historical periods. and the political framework is hampered by existing difficulties.

In order for interstate economic and social relations to achieve more effective results, it is necessary to connect with distant countries of the world, in other words, macro-spaces. But in terms of economic relations with the rest of the world, it has a number of disadvantages for the countries on the mainland. faces the layers. Uzbekistan is macroeconomically close to the seas, as it is one of the few countries in the world that must cross the territory of at least two countries.

geographical location (relative to the rest of the world). During the years of independence, Uzbekistan was recognized by the world in various directions and actively participated in international road projects connecting the ocean, which eases this situation a little.

Summary. It can be concluded from this article that the entire network, both social and economic, cannot be imagined without transport, because the main highway connecting the country with other countries is transport, and its development ensures significant economic growth of the country. Many countries use the transport network as an effective means of communication to develop their economy. One of the main reasons for this is its convenience, cheap and reliable communication between countries.

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